

New Copper(II) Complexes with Tridentate Dibasic ONS Donor Ligands

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New copper(II) complexes with the Schiff bases derived from thiosemicarbazide and acetoacetanilide, acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide, acetoacet-*o*-anisidide, acetoacet-*o*-toluidide, benzoyl-acetanilide and *m*-nitrobenzoylacetanilide have been synthesised and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, electronic and infrared spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The Schiff bases behave as dibasic tridentate O, N and S donor ligands forming complexes with 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The complexes exhibit subnormal magnetic moments ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.14\text{--}1.25$ B. M.) and are involved in anti-ferromagnetic exchange. The negative J values ($361\text{--}402$ cm⁻¹) of the complexes indicate that the complexes have $S=O$ ground state. The complexes exhibit a ligand field band at around 16000 cm⁻¹ and a charge transfer band at around 28000 cm⁻¹.

CCOORDINATION complexes of dibasic tridentate ligands are of considerable research interest because of the possibility of dimetallation leading to metal complexes with unusual magnetic properties¹. In case of copper(II) most of the studies have veered around ONO donor ligands and there is no report on complexes with SSS donor ligands. Work on copper(II) complexes containing tridentate mixed sulphur ligands is also very limited². We describe here the synthesis of copper(II) complexes with mixed sulphur ligand Schiff bases (I) which are of biological importance because thiosemicarbazones possess toxophoric nature^{3,4}. Several metal complexes of thiosemicarbazone derivatives are reported to possess activity against viruses, tumours and fungi^{4,5}.

I. $R = \text{CH}_3$, $R' = \text{H}$, *o*-Cl, *o*-CH₃O, *o*-OH;
 $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $R' = \text{H}$, *m*-NO₂.

Experimental

Materials: Copper(II) acetate monohydrate was BDH AnalaR product. Thiosemicarbazide was purchased from IDPL. Acetoacetanilide, *o*-chloroacetoacetanilide, acetoacet-*o*-anisidide and acetoacet-*o*-toluidide were obtained from Colour Chem. Ltd., Bombay. Benzoylacetanilide and *m*-nitrobenzoyl-

acetanilide were prepared by the literature methods^{6,7}.

Physical measurements and analysis: The IR spectra were recorded in nujol with the help of Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer using polystyrene as calibrant. The reflectance spectra were recorded on Beckman DU recording spectrophotometer attached with a reflectance arrangement. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the standard. The magnetic susceptibilities were corrected for temperature-independent paramagnetism term (60×10^{-6} cgs unit) and diamagnetic contribution of metal ligand system⁸. Copper was estimated iodometrically after igniting the complexes to copper oxide, dissolving the oxide in analar HCl and finally titrating with standard Na₂S₂O₈ solution to starch end point. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically by fusing the compound with fusion mixture (Na₂O₂ and NaOH) in a nickel crucible and finally precipitating as BaSO₄. Analytical data are given in Table I.

Preparation of Schiff bases: β -Diketone (5 mmol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.45 g; 5 mmol) were mixed in MeOH (25 ml) and refluxed on a steam bath for 1 hr. The partial evaporation of solvent under a current of air gave crystals of Schiff bases which were suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Yield = 80%.

Preparation of the complexes: Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O (1.0 g; 5 mmol) was dissolved in hot MeOH (25 ml) and the solution was filtered. A methanolic solution of the Schiff base (5 mmol in 30 ml) was slowly added to the filtrate. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 hr. The separated

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY, IR AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compound/Stoichiometry	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M. (Temp. K)	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ cm^{-1} complex (ligand)	ν_{max} cm^{-1}
	Cu	N	S			
Cu(acetoacetanilide-TSC*)	19.9	17.6	10.4	1.23	1590	15600,
$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_4\text{SCu}$	(20.89)	(17.98)	(10.27)	(293)	(1600)	28570
Cu(acetoacet- <i>o</i> -chloroanilide-TSC)	17.9	16.6	9.5	1.18	1595	16200,
$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_4\text{SClCu}$	(18.85)	(16.18)	(9.25)	(293)	(1600)	28600
Cu(acetoacet- <i>o</i> -aniside-TSC)	18.8	16.2	9.5	1.17	1600	16400,
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{SCu}$	(18.59)	(16.40)	(9.37)	(292)	(1615)	28300
Cu(acetoacet- <i>o</i> -toluidide-TSC)	19.9	16.8	9.9	1.14	1595	15500,
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_4\text{SCu}$	(19.51)	(17.20)	(9.88)	(293)	(1600)	28000
Cu(benzoylacetanilide-TSC)	16.4	14.8	8.5	1.19	1600	17500,
$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_4\text{SCu}$	(17.00)	(14.99)	(8.57)	(305)	(1620)	29000
Cu(<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoylacetanilide-TSC)	15.6	16.4	7.8	1.25	1620	17200,
$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{SCu}$	(15.17)	(16.73)	(7.65)	(306)	(1625)	26300

* TSC = thiosemicarbazide.

greenish grey compound was suction filtered, washed thoroughly with MeOH and dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Yield = 70%. The complexes are insoluble in water and common non-coordinating solvents.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data for the complexes indicate 1 : 1 copper : ligand stoichiometry and hence the Schiff bases act as dibasic tridentate ligands. The dibasic tridentate character of the ligands forces the copper(II) ion to dimerise or polymerise. This is reflected in the insolubility of the complexes in common non-coordinating organic solvents and water and the decomposition of the complexes at $>250^\circ$ without melting. The magnetic susceptibility data also support this fact. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes are in the range of 1.14-1.25 B.M. which is remarkably less than the spin-only moment of 1.73 B.M. required for an $S = 1/2$ system like $3d^9$ copper(II). The low magnetic moments are attributed to the antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between the neighbouring copper(II) ions. The exchange integral, J , of the complexes was calculated from the room temperature magnetic susceptibility data using the Bleaney Bowers equation⁹ and the J values are in the range 361-402 cm^{-1} . The negative J values indicate the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange with $S = 0$ ground state. J values do not change appreciably with the change of substituents (R, R' in I). This indicates that the electronic effect of substitution in copper(II) complexes is relatively unimportant.

The electronic spectra exhibit a broad asymmetric band centred at around 16000 cm^{-1} which is assigned to $d-d$ transitions. The complexes show a band at around 28000 cm^{-1} assignable to copper $\rightarrow$ ligand charge transfer transition rather than to dimetallic species¹⁰. Electrical conductance, molecular weight and single crystal X-ray studies could not be made because of the insolubility of the complexes in common solvents.

In the ir spectra of the ligands the absence of a band around 2500 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{SH})$ indicates the

thione nature of the ligands in the solid state. The free ligands exhibit a strong band in the range 1120-1185 cm^{-1} which is assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretch¹¹. On complex formation this band disappears indicating coordination through sulphur atom with the conversion of $\text{C}=\text{S}$ to $\text{C}-\text{S}$. A new band simultaneously appears in the 655-710 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ stretch^{12,13}. Many authors have attributed two bands at 1180-1320 and ~ 830 cm^{-1} to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretch in non-coordinated thiosemicarbazide derivatives¹⁴. We wish to point out that there cannot be two bands due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretch. The ~ 1150 cm^{-1} band should be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and the ~ 830 cm^{-1} band to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ stretch and $\pi(\text{C}-\text{H})$ in the ligands. However, in thiosemicarbazide derivatives where thiolisation takes place one may observe the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ stretch at ~ 650 cm^{-1} . The ir spectra of all the ligands exhibit a sharp band around 1650 cm^{-1} due to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and this indicates the non-involvement of the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of anilide moiety in the Schiff base formation as the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ due to acetyl or benzoyl moiety occurs comparatively at higher energy (~ 1700 cm^{-1})¹⁵. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band disappears in the complexes due to enolisation and consequent coordination. A strong band at ~ 1620 cm^{-1} in free ligands due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch shifts to lower energy by 5-20 cm^{-1} indicating coordination of nitrogen atom of azomethine group of Schiff bases¹⁶. The ir spectral studies indicate that the bonding sites are O, N and S in the complexes. Thus, the analytical and ir data and the valence requirement of the metal ion indicate the tridentate dibasic behaviour of the ligands.

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